

**IMPACT OF THE ACADEMIC STRESS ON THE PERFORMANCE
OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: A CASE STUDY OF PANJAB**

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

HIGHLIGHTS

- Existence of stress in our daily life
- Impact of stress on students
- Stress management
- Suggestions
- Limitations
- conclusion
- implications

IMPACT ON STUDENTS

- Academic records
- Poor Management skills
- Memory problems
- Constant worry
- Self defeating thoughts
- Short temper
- Social withdrawal
- Concentration difficulties

STRESS MANAGEMENT

- Look forward
- Do Exercises
- Use of YOGA & MEDITATION
- Management of academic activities
- Differentiation
- Positive behavior

ABSTRACT

World is dynamic. Thus changes are all pervasive. Due to changes, legion strains have been facing by human in every sphere of life. Stress is one of them which is being fronted by human to maximum extent. It is saying that it is a big word having bigger impact on all of us. However this can be solved by bringing small changes in our daily life. Recently Academic stress is the burning issue which is badly impacting academic performance of students. This current study evinces that academic stress badly impacted performance of students. The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of academic stress on Indian students. The primary data for this study has been gathered from 500 different students from different universities by raising five point rating LIKERT SCALE (Always=4, Often=3, Unsure=2, Sometimes=1, Never=0). In order to analyze data, Regression, correlation and CRONBACH ALPHA were utilized by using software SPSS version 22.0. Results showed significant impact of academic stress on academic performance of students.

Keywords: Academic stress, Academic performance, Impact, Indian students, Suggestions

INTRODUCTION

Everybody knows stress. That is why, now a day's stress has become an important subject matter in our society. Sometimes it motivates us to get that promotion at work or reach at destination. But if we are unable to handle it, then it makes our life hell for long time. It creates problems for our job, family life and health. Stephanie Watson (2020) revealed that more than 50% Americans fight with their friends and loved ones because of stress and more than 70% are suffering physical and mental symptoms from it. Stress takes place when he deals with irresistible situation which is unmanageable.

Actually it arises when any person feels burden and it exceeds his available assets. These days its existence is omnipresent and specifically in students. It has become a part and parcel of his life. A strong relationship has been traced between stressful life and reduced academic performance among students (Dusselier, Dunn, Wang, Shelley and Whalen, 2005, Mishra and Mckean.2000).

NEED OF THE STUDY

Today we are living in competitive world which is changing day by day. This competitive world has been changing every area like social, political, economic, health and academic. Academic area is the area which is mostly impacting and creating academic stress among students. This academic stress is badly impacting physical and mental health of the students. In spite of it, this academic stress also impacts academic performance, sleep quality, concentration, memory loss etc. Students are the future pillars of every country who are responsible to reach their nation to the zenith point of progress. Thus it was necessary to do some research to examine the impact of academic stress among students in order to mitigate it in the coming future.

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

This study will bring those variables which cause academic stress among students. This current study will help various universities to propound new ways in order to mitigate academic stress among students. This study will also help researchers to get up to date information for doing further study in the coming future.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Mussarat & Seema (2013)¹ revealed that perceived academic stress has significant effect of stress on students performance. For this study, primary data had been collected from various students

Jayanti Tarugu (2015)² studied on academic stress among higher secondary students and concluded that academic stress was higher in male urban students than female rural students. For this study data was collected from 250 XI standard students, studying in higher secondary schools on simple random sampling. It was also resulted that more academic was reported in private schools as compare to private schools.

Reddy, Menon and Thatti ((2018)³ examined the impact of academic stress and its sources among university students. The students were taken from commerce, management, humanities and basic sciences. Quantitative research design had been employed on four dimensions like personal adequacy, fear of failure, interpersonal difficulties with teachers and teacher pupil relationship. This study revealed high stress in professional courses as compare to non professional course

Pascoe, Hatrick and Parker (2019)⁵ studied on impact of stress on students in secondary school and higher education and concluded that academic stress is the main reason for secondary and territory students. This stress creates negative impact on student's learning capacity, academic performance, education and employment attainment, sleep quality and quantity, physical health, mental health and substance use outcomes. In order to solve this problem, stress management skills and abilities must be employed in students.

RESEARCH GAP

Review of literature reports that only few studies have been conducted in India regarding this area. Mostly these are theoretical not empirically ones. This current study is empirical which has taken those variables which are ignored by the previous researchers. Thus this study will throw some light on non study variables that will help universities in order to mitigate academic stress among students in the coming days

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

After going through review of literature, the following objectives have been propounded. The main objective of this study is to establish the impact of academic stress on Indian students. However this study will cover the following specific objectives:

- 1) To examine the impact of academic stress on academic records of students under study
- 2) To examine the impact of academic stress on management skills of students under study
- 3) To examine the impact of academic stress on memory of students under study
- 4) To examine the impact of academic stress on worry and anxiety of students under study
- 5) To examine the impact of academic stress on self defeating thoughts of students under study
- 6) To examine the impact of academic stress on irritation and temper of students under study
- 7) To examine the impact of academic stress on social withdrawals of students under study
- 8) To examine the impact of academic stress on concentration of students under study

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

It is expected that academic performance is being impacted by academic stress. Thus this current study has taken academic stress as the dependent variable while academic records, management skills, memory, worry and anxiety, self defeating thoughts, irritation, social withdrawals and concentration are taken as independent variables

DEPENDENT VARIABLE**INDEPENDENT VARIABLES****TESTABLE HYPOTHESES:**

On the basis of upper stated objectives, the following hypotheses have been tested:

H01: There is no relationship between impacts of academic stress on academic records of students under study

H02: There is no relationship between impacts of academic stress and management skills of students under study

H03: There is no relationship between impacts of academic stress on memory of students under study

H04: There is no relationship between impacts of academic stress on worry and anxiety of students under study

H05: There is no relationship between impacts of academic stress on self defeating thoughts of students under study

H06: There is no relationship between impacts of academic stress on concentration of students under study

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

INSTRUMENT

It used five point rating LIKERT scale ranging from “0” to “4” (Always=4, Often=3, Unsure=2, Sometimes=1, Never=0) including 24 items.

SAMPLE

This study has utilized the sample of 500 students from five universities students. located in Punjab ie Guru Nanak Dev university, Chandigarh University, Punjab University Chandigarh, Panjabi university Patiala and Lovely university Jalandhar by using purpose sampling technique

PROCEDURE

The data was gathered from students by Google form and were instructed to complete the scale by giving response to every item in the questionnaire .It was assured that given information will be kept confidential.

DATA PROCESSING AND ANALYZING

Data was entered, edited and analyzed by using SPSS -22 Version through CRONBACH's Alpha, Correlation and Regression.

RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY

In order to check the internal reliability and validity, CRONBACH'S ALPHA Coefficient of a psychometric test score was utilized for six variables. The instrument has an acceptable level of reliability as more than 0.70 for all the scales.

CRONBACH's ALPHA for reliability of study variables

Independent variables	CRONBACH's Alpha	No of items
Academic record	.87	4
Management skills	.84	4
Memory	.80	4
Worry & Anxiety	.88	4
Self Defeating Thoughts	.85	4
Concentration	.81	4

The highest reliability was reported for 'Worry and Anxiety' (alpha =.88), followed by 'Academic Record' (alpha=.87), followed by 'Self Defeating Thoughts' (alpha=.85), followed by 'Management Skills (alpha=.84), followed by Concentration (alpha=.81), followed by 'Memory' (alpha =.80).

Thus the impact of academic stress can be studied under six major constructs namely academic records, management skills, memory, worry and anxiety, self defeating thoughts and concentration

CORRELATION

	Academic stress (DV)	Academic records (IV-1)	Management skills (IV-2)	Memory (IV-3)	Worry and anxiety (IV-4)	Self Defeating thoughts (IV-5)	Concentration (IV-6)
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Academ ic stress		-.77	-.71	-.63	-.79	-.74	-.72
Pearson Correlat ion	1						
Sig(2- tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
N	500	500	500	500	500	500	500

The current study employed correlation analysis in order to measure the inter-relationship between independent variables and dependent variable. This table shows significant relationships between dependent variable and independent variables. The correlation of worry and anxiety is $-.79$ that shows large negative impact on academic performance. The correlation of academic records is $-.77$ that shows negative relationship between academic records and academic performance. This also shows that self defeating thoughts and academic performance has negative relationship. The correlation of concentration is $-.72$ that shows large negative impact of it on academic performance. The correlation of the last independent variable ie management skills is $-.63$ that also shows large negative impact of it on academic performance.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

This study utilized regression analysis in order to evaluate and understand the relationships between the dependent and independent variables.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std Error of the estimate
1	.70a	.49	.453	-.377

- a. Predictors: (Constants) Academic Records, Management Skills, Memory, Worry and Anxiety, Self Defeating Thoughts, Concentration
- b. Dependent variable: Academic Performance

This table shows the model summary in which value of R is .70. This shows that there is strong correlation between dependent variable and independent variables. Here the value of Adjusted R Square is .49 that shows that our model is good fit. Therefore our all alternative hypotheses will be accepted because of significance value less than 0.05. This shows that all independent variables have impact on dependent variable academic performance.

ANNOVA

Model	Sum of square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig
1 regression	3.093	4	95.3725	7.413	.290
residual	7.222	2	3.611		
Total	10.315	6			

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Academic Records, Management Skills, Memory, Worry and Anxiety, Self Defeating Thoughts, Concentration
- b. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance

This table shows that significance value of F (.2900) which is less than 0.05. This describes that all independent variables have done their good jobs in explaining dependent variable.

Table 5

- a. Coefficients table of impact of academic stress against the independent variables (Academic Records, Management Skills, Memory, Worry and Anxiety, Self

Defeating Thoughts, Concentration (coefficients)

Model	Un-Standardized coefficients		Std coefficients	Beta	T
	B	Std error			
Constants	3.376	.0132	-----	25.75	.000
Academic records	.87	.042	.095	1.68	.023
	.274	.034	.033	6.808	.033
Management skills	.424	.0185	.0185	6.890	.043
Memory	.134	.575	.075	2.73	.037
Worry and anxiety	.234	.321	.074	4.34	.016
Self defeating thoughts	.431	.451	.56	7.43	.035
Concentration	.564	.321	.65	4.32	.34

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Response Rate

This study obtained excellent response rate according to table of Babbie (1990)

TABLE -6 OF BABBIE (1990)

Adequate	50%
Good	60%
Very good	70%
Excellent	Above 70%

The study issued 500 questionnaires from which 500 filled questionnaires were returned. This brought the response rate to 100%.

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF IMPACT OF ACADEMIC STRESS ON INDIAN STUDENTS

A very high percentage of respondents (90%) revealed that academic stress always worsens grading performance. (100%) respondents informed that academic stress makes always students failure to maximum extent. All respondents informed that academic stress often impacts sleep quality of students. On the other hand (83.33%) of respondents revealed that academic stress always creates irritation and short temper among students.

IMPACT OF ACADEMIC STRESS ON ACADEMIC RECORDS

(60%) of the respondents always agreed that academic stress decreases CGPA while (70%) were also revealed that academic stress always impacts their future performance. 70% respondents mentioned that academic stress often makes calculations wrong. 100% of the respondents revealed that academic stress always puzzles them. Thus it can be concluded that academic stress deeply influences academic performance.

IMPACT OF ACADEMIC STRESS ON MANAGEMENT SKILLS

63% of the respondents revealed that academic stress always decreases management ability of students while (80%) told that academic stress often narrows thinking ability. (86%)

respondents announced that academic stress makes always student mentally ill .60% of respondents announced that academic stress often makes routine work unmanageable. Thus it can be concluded that academic stress badly impacts academic performance to maximum extent.

IMPACT OF ACADEMIC STRESS ON MEMORY

(66%) of the respondents announced that academic stress always makes students oblivious Only (63%) of the respondents told that It is always impossible to defend ourselves from academic stress while studying. 66.66% of the respondents marked that academic stress often badly impacts learning power. (80%) of respondents revealed that academic stress always increases memory loss. Thus it can be concluded that academic stress badly impacts academic performance

IMPACT OF ACADEMIC STRESS ON WORRY AND ANXIETY

(80%) respondents marked that academic stress makes often students restless. While (90%) of the respondents announced that academic stress always takes the focus off important tasks to be completed timely.86% of the respondents revealed that academic stress makes always constant worry. (100%) of respondents strongly informed that academic stress sometimes makes assignment miss. Thus it can be concluded that academic stress badly impacts performance of students

IMPACT OF ACADEMIC STRESS ON SELF DEFEATING THOUGHTS

(90%) respondents revealed that academic stress often makes students consistently thinking and (83%) of the respondents revealed that academic stress always makes students weaken in solving their problems. While 66% of the respondents informed that academic stress always makes students weaken in focusing on failures. (100%) of respondents informed that academic stress often makes students weaken in solving adverse situation. Thus it can be concluded that academic stress badly impacts performance of students

IMPACT OF ACADEMIC STRESS ON CONCENTRATION

(90%) respondents marked that academic stress makes always poor concentration of students. While (100%) of the respondents announced that academic stress always makes it difficult to memorize things timely.89% of the respondents revealed that academic stress

makes always difficult for students to think critically. (90%) of respondents strongly informed that academic stress always makes difficult for students to think optimally. . Thus it can be concluded that academic stress badly impacts performance of students

ANALYSIS OF HYPOTHESES

IMPACT OF ACADEMIC STRESS ON ACADEMIC RECORDS

(60%) of the respondents always agreed that academic stress decreases CGPA while (70%) were also revealed that academic stress always impacts their future performance.70% respondents mentioned that academic stress often makes calculations wrong. 100% of the respondents revealed that academic stress always puzzles them. Thus it can be concluded that academic stress deeply influences academic performance.

Thus the hypothesis (H01) that There is no relationship between impacts of academic stress on academic records of students under study to be rejected.

IMPACT OF ACADEMIC STRESS ON MANAGEMENT SKILLS

63% of the respondents revealed that academic stress always decreases management ability of students while (80%) told that academic stress often narrows thinking ability. (86%) respondents announced that academic stress makes always student mentally ill .60% of respondents announced that academic stress often makes routine work unmanageable. Thus it can be concluded that academic stress badly impacts academic performance to maximum extent.

Thus the hypothesis (H02) that there is no relationship between impacts of academic stress and management skills of students under study stands to be rejected

IMPACT OF ACADEMIC STRESS ON MEMORY

(66%) of the respondents announced that academic stress always makes students oblivious Only (63%) of the respondents told that It is always impossible to defend ourselves from academic stress while studying. 66.66% of the respondents marked that academic stress often badly impacts learning power. (80%) of respondents revealed that academic stress always increases memory loss. Thus it can be concluded that academic stress badly impacts

academic performance

Thus the hypothesis (H03) that there is no relationship between impacts of academic stress on memory of students under study stands to be rejected

IMPACT OF ACADEMIC STRESS ON WORRY AND ANXIETY

(80%) respondents marked that academic stress makes often students restless. While (90%) of the respondents announced that academic stress always takes the focus off important tasks to be completed timely. 86% of the respondents revealed that academic stress makes always constant worry. (100%) of respondents strongly informed that academic stress sometimes makes assignment miss. Thus it can be concluded that academic stress badly impacts performance of students

Thus the hypothesis (H04) that there is no relationship between impacts of academic stress on memory of students under study stands to be rejected.

IMPACT OF ACADEMIC STRESS ON SELF DEFEATING THOUGHTS

(90%) respondents revealed that academic stress often makes students consistently thinking and (83%) of the respondents revealed that academic stress always makes students weaken in solving their problems. While 66% of the respondents informed that academic stress always makes students weaken in focusing on failures. (100%) of respondents informed that academic stress often makes students weaken in solving adverse situation. Thus it can be concluded that academic stress badly impacts performance of students

Thus the hypothesis (H04) that there is no relationship between impacts of academic stress on memory of students under study stands to be rejected.

IMPACT OF ACADEMIC STRESS ON CONCENTRATION

(90%) respondents marked that academic stress makes always poor concentration of students. While (100%) of the respondents announced that academic stress always makes it difficult to memorize things timely. 89% of the respondents revealed that academic stress makes always difficult for students to think critically. (90%) of respondents strongly informed that academic stress always makes difficult for students to think optimally. Thus it can be concluded that academic stress badly impacts performance of students

Thus the hypothesis (H04) that there is no relationship between impacts of academic stress on concentration of students under study stands to be rejected.

STRESS MANAGEMENT

There are some ways which must be employed by students in order to reduce academic stress in the future

- Concentrate yourself only on look forward everyday because it will help you to anticipate tomorrow.
- Do exercise regularly because it will dampen depression and stress
- Do YOGA and MEDITATION daily
- Manage your academic activities more efficiently
- Try to understand your academic capabilities
- Differentiate yourself what is expected of you and not to have unreasonable expectations
- Surround yourself with positive behavior

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The findings of this current study point towards certain study implications. Firstly this study brought the impact of academic stress on Indian students. This study will help universities to mitigate stress among students by formulating effective strategies on the basis of the studied variables. The study revealed that there is an acceptance of impact of academic stress on Indian students by studying variables like Academic Records, Management Skills, Memory, Worry and Anxiety, Self Defeating Thoughts and Concentration

Thus the findings of this research can help the universities in the formulation of policies and practices for reducing stress among students in the future.

LIMITATIONS OF THIS STUDY

Though this study throws light on impact of academic stress on Indian students, it is not exhaustive. Thus it is not free from limitations.

- 1 The sample size for the collection of primary data was limited to 500 respondents only.
- 2 This study has covered only five universities only.
3. The findings and suggestions are based on the information collected through questionnaires from respondents.
- 4 Cost and time constraints.

In spite of above limitations, this study is very helpful to universities since it throws light on the impact of academic stress on Indian students.

SCOPE FOR FURTHER STUDY

The main objective of this study was to throw light on impact of academic stress on Indian students. This is not the end research of this constructs. Thus the study suggests a few aspects for further study in the future.

- 1) The present study investigated impact of academic stress on Indian students. Further studies can be conducted by considering other variables.
- 2) Further study can be conducted by applying different methodologies.
- 3) Studies similar in nature and scope can be conducted in other area of India.

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